

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE CONQUER OF KARAKALPAK LAND BY RUSSIAN TROOPS (1873)

Bekbaulieva Nasiba

Karakalpak State University, doktorant, Nukus, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract

This article examines in detail the reasons behind the military campaigns of Tsarist Russia against the lands of the Karakalpaks and the Khivan Khanate. Firstly, based on archival data, the article investigates the number of armed forces that attacked the Khivan Khanate under the leadership of General Governor of Turkestan, von K.P.Kaufman. Based on historical evidence, the article mentions the aggressive movements into the territories of Kungrad, Khojeyli, and Mangyt, where the Russian army reached through the Orenburg and Mangyshlak detachments after the defeat of the Khivan Khanate.

In particular, the article highlights the military operations that occurred in the city of Mangyt, with additions from the information of M.Y.Bayaniy and Colonel M.Ali Khanav-Avarsky. Alongside this, the article examines the drafting of the Gendimiyan Agreement, a treaty concluded as a result of the seizure of the lands of the Karakalpaks and the Khivan Khanate.

Keywords: Tsarist Russia, K.P.Kaufman, Khivan Khanate, Turkestan, Orenburg, Amu Darya, Kungrad, Mangyt.

The crusade against Khiva had been prepared for a long time. On December 4, 1872, a special council was held under the leadership of the king in order to determine the beginning of the crusade. At this meeting, Turkestan General-Governor Von K.P. Kaufman made a statement about Russia's politics in Central Asia. In the spring of 1873, the Council adopted a resolution to launch a crusade against Khiva.

The crusade was supposed to be implemented by Turkestan, Orenburg and Caucasus districts. General-governor of Turkestan von K.P. Kaufman was confirmed as the leader of crusade. According to the resolution of the Council, "Khiva should not be annexed to Russia, but to improve trade relations between the two countries, it should be subject to Russia, like other neighboring Central Asian nations."

The crusade to Khiva was agreed upon internationally. Russia normalized relations with Afghanistan and Iran. In 1873, Russia-England signed a treaty. According to this, Russia was to consider the part of Afghanistan made up of Uzbeks, Kazakhs, Karakalpaks, Turkmens, and Tajiks called "Afghanistan Turkestan" as "Afghanistan Region". Russia and England reaches peace.

Only after this, the Khiva crusade of 1873 begins. The invasion was carried out by the joint army of Turkestan, Caucasian and Orenburg military forces. The army participating in the invasion is divided into Turkestan, Orenburg, Caucasian detachments, Mangyshlak, Krasnovodsk, Jizzakh, Kazaly columns. The Jizzakh convoy had to leave Tashkent and travel 900 km to Khiva. The Kazaly column was closer to Khiva than Jizzakh, but it did not have the right to go to Khiva. The farthest Orenburg detachment had to travel at least 1400 km to Khiva. The Caucasian detachment left the Caspian coast and had to travel 800 km to Khiva. In the second half of May, 1873, the Caucasian and Mangyslak detachments had to join each other on the border of Amudarya.

According to A.I. Maksheev, the strength of the military force that participated in the offensive against Khiva was as follows: Turkestan detachment - 5300 people, 22 groups, 8 rocket launchers; Orenburg detachment - 3500 people, 12 groups, 6 rocket launchers; Caucasian detachment - 4300 people, 22 groups, 8 rocket launchers; a total of 13,100 people, 56 groups, 20 rocket launchers [1,314]. General M.A. Terentyev's report is similar to the figures below: 12,248 people, 56 groups, 17 rocket launchers participated [2,262].

On March 1, 1873, the first division of the Jizzakh column under the leadership of Major-General Golovachev left Tashkent, and the second division left Khozhent on March 11. The leader K. P. Kaufman was also in this detachment. Two parts of the Jizzakh column connect to each other at the place "Arys Bel-Kudyk" at a distance of 280 km from Jizzakh. They were waiting for the Kazaly convoy until April 11.

One part of the Kazaly column left Kazaly on March 6, and the second part left Perovsk fortress on March 8 and joined the Jizzakh column on April 12.

After this, the whole Turkestan detachment under the leadership of K. P. Kaufman reached Amudarya on May 10, experiencing many difficulties along the way. On May 21, Kaufman's army, along the river, reached the Sheikh-Aryk side of Amudarya. The hypocrites try to avoid this. However, one or two shots fired by the Russian group killed them, and the Russian army passed to the border of the Darya without much resistance. Takes Pitniak, Hazarasp without difficulty. Kaufmann's army marched to Khiva on May 27 without any further resistance.

The Orenburg detachment left Orenburg, Orsk and Uralsk in February and arrived in Emba on March 18. On April 16, the Orenburg detachment reached the Isen-Shagy grove on the back-western shore of the Aral Sea. He traveled along the western side of the Aral Sea and arrived in Urge on May 6. From there, it reached

Kungrat on May 8, thanks to Lake Aibuyir, which dried up at that time.

The Mangyshlak detachment under the command of Colonel Lomakin reached the Aibugir Lake at this time. Hearing that the Orenburg detachment entered Konyrat, the front part of the Mangyshlak detachment entered Konyrat on May 12. On May 14, the entire Mangyshlak detachment joined the Orenburg detachment.

These two combined detachments under the leadership of Lieutenant General Verevkin took Khozheli on May 15. On May 20, he received Mangyt. "Because they came to hunt a great game in the Mangyt valley," - Bayani wrote about them. Verevkin ordered: "Russian soldiers attacked the village, massacred the inhabitants regardless of men, women and young, and then razed the village to the ground. After that, not being satisfied with this, the inhabitants of Mangyt came to Mangyt Castle, surrendered the castle to Russia and returned safely. Because they finished killing without leaving a living being, they left the city under fire" [5,214].

Colonel M. Alikhanov-Avarky testified about such nonsense: "I am in Mangit. The dead are lying among the property scattered in the streets and yards. I saw an Uzbek running across the street in a desperate situation. A cossack is targeting him... the poor thing fell to the ground. By the way, such an incident also happened in Mangit: a tall old man who was barely walking through a narrow street was cut in two places with a sword, blood was pouring out of his bare head and running down his face and beard. A drunken cossack in a white fur coat with a blood-stained sword is chasing after him.

Walking around Manghit, I came across the stream that flows through the city. I saw a few women in it, who were drowning in water up to their necks, their faces changed from fear, and my heart jumped and pulled me back. Not far from them, under the trees by the stream and in a narrow place between the walls, several elderly men and women were hiding. Perhaps they were also trembling and waiting for the moment of their death... As soon as they saw me, they all knelt down and began to cry, begging for safety" [6,209].

Captures Qitay on May 22, stopping 8 km short of Khiva on May 27 without encountering any significant opposition [1,321].

The Krasnovodsk column, commanded by Colonel Markozov, passed through Karakum without drinking water, could not reach Khiva, and then returned. Apart from this column, all the army forces that took part in the attack gathered near Khiva on May 29. On May 28, Verevkin's Orenburg and Mangyshlak detachments stopped at the wall of Khiva. Kaufman stopped 20 km from Khiva.

On May 28, around 17.00, representatives of the Khan came to Kaufman's camp. They said that the khanate would be handed over without a fight. Kaufman also writes to the Russian Minister of Defense D. A. Milyutin.

Khiva Khan's representative asked Kaufman to stop shooting at Khiva from now on. In particular, Verevkin's detachment stood before entering Khiva

and fired non-stop. On May 28, Verevkin was wounded in the face in a shootout.

Kaufman ordered that only the khan himself would talk to me about the full coverage of Khiva, but before entering Khiva on May 29, the khan himself would appear before me. In addition, he orders Verevkin to stop shooting at Khiva because it is not necessary.

On May 29, in the morning, the Turkestan detachment under the leadership of Kaufman left the Yangi-Aryk camp and marched to Khiva. At eight o'clock in the morning, he reaches the outer wall of Khiva and stops. Meanwhile, the Khan's brother Seyd-Emir Uly Umar, his middle brother Atajan-Tore, and his cousin Irtazaly Inak appear in front of Kaufman.

They say that Muhammed Rahim Khan abandoned the khanate and fled to the Turkmen cause with Matmurat Diwanbeg and the forces against Muhammed Rahim in Khiva joined forces and appointed Atajan as the khan instead.

After the departure of the Khan and his mercenary Turkmen troops from Khiva, there was no force left in the city to resist the Russian army. In this regard, General Terentyev said, "Khiva did not show any resistance. Only small forces fought against us", he says, "Khiva's Khan did not use any means to defend himself, even to defeat the Russians" [3,109].

General Verevkin's army breached the Shahabad Gate and entered Khiva. Kaufman's detachment with the Khazarasp gate enters.

On June 2, Muhammed Rahim Khan, who fled to the cause of the Turkmens, came to the Kaufman stake. As a result of the negotiations, Muhammed Rahim was left as Khan of Khiva again. K. P. Kaufman wrote about this in his message to St. Petersburg: "...I accepted the Khan. Now, with all due respect, "I allow him to rule the khanate on the basis of the "Provisional rule" [4,32].

General M.A. Terentyev writes: "Representatives of the nomadic Karakalpaks who lived on the shores of Amudarya also came to the deputations that arrived on June 10. They requested to transfer the Karakalpaks to the Russian republic. He asked them to think about this issue carefully. However, they returned two days later and repeated their request. This problem was taken into account when creating the agreement contract. And because of the land that was given to us on the right side of the river, their settlements were also added to us" [1,32].

On June 6, von K.P. Kaufmann signed the regulation on the management of the khanate during the temporary stay of the Russian army in this region. "Devon" was created under the leadership of Khan. It includes the representative of the Russians and the chief officials of Khiva. "Devon" considers 4 issues at its meeting: to provide all the means to supply the Russian army during its stay in the khanate and to take them safely to their destination when they return; emancipation of all slaves in the kingdom; different Turkmen tribes (Yavmyts, Shavdyrs, Imraly Turkmens) who were hostile to the Russian army during the Battle of Khiva. It is necessary to receive a contribution from the khanate.

On June 12, a document on the abolition of slavery in the Khanate was signed. Approximately, the number of Persian slaves in Khiva Khanate reached 40 thousand. Most of them are returned to their countries from time to time.

On August 12, Russia signed an 18-point peace treaty with Khiva Khanate. According to this agreement, Khiva Khanate is declared as a state belonging to Russia. Khiva becomes a semi-khanate.

The Khanate of Khiva did not completely join Russia. The reason is that already in the 60s of the XIX century, the British government demanded that the regions of the Central Asian khanates located in the Syrdarya and Amudarya basins, i.e. Khiva, Bukhara and Kokand khanates, should remain a unified region. That is why, at the time of the Khiva crusade, the Tsar's government had to think about not only overcoming the waterless desert on the way to Khiva, but also overcoming the diplomatic problems that were brewing in London.

The Russian government was forced to preserve the khan's rule in Khiva and declare Khiva as a state in its own right. The intractability of the problem was known to Russia even before the beginning of the battle of Khiva. However, Khiva lost their right to

communicate with the neighboring Turkmens and Bukhara without the permission of Russia, the Khan's army was purged, the territory of the khanate on the right side of Amudarya was flourished and its people were transferred to Russia. Khiva had to pay a military contribution to Russia in the amount of 2 million 200 thousand rubles for 20 years from 1873 to 1893.

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